

Cooperative Societies and Adoption of Improved Agricultural Technologies Among FADAMA Rice Farmers in Enugu State.

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Abstract

This paper examines cooperative rice farmers and their level of adoption of improved technologies in FADAMA rice farming. The study sought to ascertain the effect of cooperative on adoption levels of improved agricultural technologies among rice farmers in Enugu state. The survey research design was chosen in this research work. The study is made up of all rice farmers' cooperative societies in Enugu state that participated in FADAMA project. According to State Department of Cooperative, there are 323 registered cooperative societies that participated in FADAMA programme out of which 48 were into rice farming. These 48 FADAMA rice farmers cooperative with membership strength of 964 constitute the population of the study. The sample size was determined through a multi-stage sampling technique. The first Stage involves a purposive selection of two LGAs that are predominantly rural and agrarian from each of the three agricultural zones in Enugu State. Second stage involved random selection of cooperatives in the selected local government area that participated in FADAMA programme.. The third stage involved selecting the cooperative societies that were into rice farming. Therefore, a total of 331 members were selected from 24 rice farmers' cooperatives who participated in FADAMA programme as sample size. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in achieving the objective of the study. Regression, frequency distribution, percentages and mean score rating were used. Findings indicate that cooperative membership had significant effect on adoption of improved agricultural technologies.

Keywords: Cooperative Societies, Agricultural Technologies, FADAMA, Rice Farmers.

Introduction

Rice is the most important grain with regard to human nutrition and caloric intake. Providing more than one-fifth of the calories consumed worldwide by humans. Rice can come in many shapes, colours and sizes (IRRI 2009). Accordingly, FADAMA III AP (206) rice will be cultivated thrice in a year by the use of irrigation. The rice plant can grow to 1-1.8m tall occasionally more depending on the variety and soil fertility. Rice can grow in different environments depending upon water availability. Generally rice does not thrive in a water logged area, yet it can survive and grow herein and it can also survive flooding.

The word “FADAMA” (in Hausa local language) means a low lying area which the National FADAMA Development programme (NFDP) was initiated following the recommendations of the World Bank in its report of 1989 titled “**Nigeria- Strategy for Agricultural Growth**”. This was meant to affect the general economic environment in Nigeria and the community specifically. Apart from the economic shift to agriculture, it is to be noted that agricultural production in Nigeria is dictated by climatic and Delphic conditions. These factors determined the range of crop planted and the efficiency of the crop production in rain fed, thus determining the agricultural production session. However, there are agricultural production systems that could be explored to support an all year round food production (especially rice) and one of such is FADAMA system of farming. It will be nice to apply modern science and technology to traditional act of farming as a way of incorporating farmers into the development stream.

Mgbada (2012) posits that technology means all those methods of production which have been developed or could be developed with the existing state of scientific knowledge. Technology helps us to do those things we need or want to do better. However, using technology that is inappropriate is at best wasteful and at worst harmful to people and the environment. It is appropriate for the task, the environment and the people. For instance, there are three levels of technology. The Nigerian farmer is using a simple hoe (low technology). The plough drawn by animals is more productive but still straight forward (intermediate technology). The tractor is highly complex (high technology) but allows one person to cultivate a larger area. Technology is basically a tool to help create development towards certain agreed overall goals.

Cooperative societies among other institutions both private and governmental have influenced agricultural technological adoption in the past. Umebali (2004) defines cooperative organization as a group of persons who have pooled themselves and their resources on self-help, mutual equitable and democratic basis to form a business enterprise, which seeks to solve the socio-economic problem(s) of its members by directly providing them with good and services in their double capacity as either owners/customers or owner/workers of the cooperative enterprise. Umebali (2004) established that it is better to deal with farmers in group (cooperative) than individual basis, hence the need for farmers in rural areas to join or form cooperatives.

This study sought to establish the effect of cooperative societies on the adoption of technologies among rice farmers.

Objectives of the study

1. To ascertain the effect of cooperative on adoption level of improved agricultural technologies among rice farmers in Enugu state.

Research Question

1. Does cooperative affect level of adoption of improved agricultural technologies among FADAMA rice farmers in Enugu State?

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Concept of Cooperation

Umebali (2004) defines cooperative organization as a group of persons who have pooled themselves and their resources on self-help, mutual equitable and democratic basis to form a business enterprise, which seeks to solve the socio-economic problem(s) of its members by directly providing them with good and services in their double capacity as either owners/customers or owner/workers of the cooperative enterprise. While Otite and Ogionwu (1994) describes cooperative society as groups made up of individuals whose inter-related tasks and specialties enable the total aggregate to achieve set goals; perform complementary and reciprocal functions, and satisfy complementary needs.

Therefore, cooperatives are focused on achieving predetermined goals from the date of formation. Okoro (2009) suggested that viable cooperative societies formed with the support of government will avail the skilled and unskilled yet willing labourers a place to fit in. One of such programmes that encourage this strategy of economic salvation is by upholding the policies of the defunct Farm Settlement Scheme and the FADAMA project, which is aimed at revamping the agricultural sector.

FADAMA

Adesoji, Farinde, and Ajayi, (2006) citing (Blench and Ingawa, 2004) describes FADAMA as an Hausa word meaning a valley-bottom, flood plain, or a lowland around a river that floods

or becomes wet when the river is high. FADAMA is defined as flood plains and lowland areas underlined by shallow aquifers and found along Nigeria's rivers system.

Adesoji, et al (2006) further suggests that FADAMAS have been sources of economic power to many groups of individuals called FADAMA Users Group (FUG). FADAMA Users Groups according to Blench and Ingawa (2004) are farmers, pastoralists, fisherfolk/fisher women, hunters and others (e.g., gatherers), who directly depend upon the natural resources of the FADAMAS for their livelihoods. FADAMAS usually flood naturally but the term is also applied to areas where people have channeled or pumped water for their farms or other purposes artificially using improved technologies. Some of the arable crops grown in the FADAMA and which the raised water table can support during the dry season are Maize (*Zea mays*) and Rice (*Oriza sativa*).

Benefit of FADAMA Agriculture Programme

NEDP (2003) reported the benefit of FADAMA Agriculture programme to include:

- i. Increased the asset base of the participant
- ii. Increased the income rates as well as changed the standard of being FADAMA farmer,
- iii. Increased the level of technical efficiency of the farmers increased the training and knowledge of the participant in low an irrigation farming and
- iv. Increased the supply and availability of food production all over the year. The report finally submitted that the programme has a positive impact on the farmers and has given them a wide potential of alleviating poverty in the country.

In Nigeria, the need to increase food production to feed the ever increasing human population and to diversify the export base of the country is more recognized now than ever before. This has turned the attention of both farmers and government to the exploitation of FADAMA lands, which are believed they have more agricultural potential than the associated upland soils, (Kparmwang & Esu, 1990; Okonkwo & Ugwa 2018; Singh & Babaji 1990; Odoanyanwu, et. al. (2017). The importance of FADAMA stems from its high level of moisture (ground water and residual moisture) even during dry season water table is close to the soil surface thus endearing FADAMA lands to farmers and making it a site of busy agricultural activities throughout the year.

Concept of Agricultural Technology

According to Torimiro and Kolawole (2008), technology is taken to mean not only machines and equipment's but also the skills, abilities, knowledge, systems and processes necessary to make things happen. Thus technology are meant to be total systems that include know-how, procedures, goods and services. Some of the identified improved technologies include fertilizer, fungicides etc. Technology is application of knowledge for practical purposes (Echetama, 2012; Okonkwo, et. al. 2017).

-Generally technology is used to improve the human environment or to carry out other social economic activities. Technology can be classified into two major categories:

- i. Material technology such as tools, equipments, agrochemicals improved seeds, improved plant varieties or hybrids, improved hybrids of animals etc.
- ii. Knowledge based technology such as the technical knowledge, management skill and other processes that farmers need to successfully grow crops or produce animal products (Susan, 2005). According to Akinbile (2007), the gap between the rich and the poor countries can largely be attributed to difference in technology. The experience of many developing countries including Nigeria bears out this statement. This countries have seriously set to acquire adopt any technology derived from scientific knowledge since the importance of the contributions of science and technology to development has never been in doubt. A symbolic relationship exist between science and technology. Science a systematic search for truth provides the bases for technology. Without technology science becomes sterile, without science technology does not exist. But it is technology, the application of technique and not science which leads to increase in productivity.

According to Ajibefun (2006), Technology is the systematic application of scientific or other organized knowledge to practical purposes and includes techniques, methods and materials.

According to him, technology as a basis for development is a product of research and can emanate from any knowledge area, be it physical, biological, social and economic. The invention of the incubator which hatches eggs in 21 days is a classical agricultural technology, so is the application of science of genetic-linkage to poultry hatchery industry – a biological technology which has revolutionized poultry production making it possible for day old chicks to be separated and hatched into male and female by sex – linked colour differences. Agricultural technologies, includes all the materials techniques practice innovation used to maximize agricultural production. High yielding varieties, mechanization, disease and pest control, fertilizer, pesticides, spacing, leeching, storming, and preservation are concluded (Mgbada, 2010).

Agricultural technologies are referred to as application of principles of technology to agricultural production processes. (Mgbada, 2002) It is the application of technology (ways of doing things) to control cauterization, growth harvesting of crops, and production of animals for food purposes. Rogers (2003), defined agricultural technology as the application of scientific knowledge or other organized knowledge methods of planting, nurturing, harvesting and processing of crops and animal. It is actually the application of technology that leads to promotion and development of agriculture. These include:

1. New breeds of crops and livestock's.
2. Use of farm chemicals such as fertilizers for disease and pest control.
3. Better ways of land preparation, cultivation, planting, social management of agricultural enterprises for optimum profit.
4. Improved cultural practices such as spacing optimum plant population region, weeding, storage, processing and preservation techniques marketing, price movement, labour and other matters that relate directly to the farmers.

Empirical Review

Asiabaka and Michelle (2002) on determinants of adoptive behavior of rural farmers in Nigeria; the major objective of the study was to assess the effect of information source and the attributes of technology on the adoptive behavior of rural farmers in Nigeria. It assessed the perception of rural farmers on the availability, credibility and degree of use of information source. The variable tested in technology attributes were complexity, availability and cost and compatibility. Data were collected from 480 farmers from southern eastern Nigeria. Findings indicated that farmer's socio-economic characteristics such as age and education influence their adoption behavior.

Musa and Abdu (2016) in their study factors influencing adoption of gum Arabic production technologies in Gombe State, Nigeria, examined the factors influencing adoption of gum Arabic production technologies in Gombe state, Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to: describe the socio - economic characteristics of gum Arabic farmers and identify factors influencing adoption of gum Arabic production technologies. Primary data were used which were collected from 46 registered gum Arabic farmers who were members of National Association of Gum Arabic Producers, Processors and Exporters of Nigeria (NAGAPPEN) Gombe state chapter. Descriptive statistics and multiple regressions were used for the analysis. The results revealed that 93.5% of the respondents were males, 97.7 were, married, and a mean age of forty nine years old, attended tertiary institutions and earned ₦M3.04 annually. Multiple regressions revealed that age (X2) educational (X5), income(X7), farming experience(X8) farm size(X9), and access to extension (X10) were significant at varying levels and positively influence the adoption of gum Arabic production technologies except age which has a negative influence. Increased government supports through sustained provision of inputs were therefore recommended among others.

Adesina and Baidu-Forson (1995) in their study on farmer's perceptions and adoption of new agricultural technology evidence from analysis in Burkina Faso and Guinea West Africa; this paper tests the hypothesis that farmer's perceptions of technology characteristics significantly affect their adoption decisions. The analysis conducted with Tobit models of modern sorghum

and rice varieties technologies in Burkina Faso and Guinea, respectively, strongly supports this hypothesis. The study shows that farmer's perception of technology characteristics significantly affects their adoption decision.

Featherstone, Ariyaratne, and Langemeier (2006) conducted a study that specifically looked at the determination of productivity growth of agricultural cooperatives. The study assesses the production growth and analyzes the extent of the growth in agricultural cooperatives. The study confirmed that rather increasing area of individual decision making unit, if the decision making units could bring together their resources and go for cooperative farming, the scale efficiency will improve. Generally, they found that agricultural cooperatives encourage technological improvement and help improvement in efficiency.

Another set of studies examining agricultural cooperative activities have explained the factors affecting the adoption of various types of cooperative activities (Katehova and Miranda, 2004, Davis and Gillespie 2007) with an overview of contrasting studies provided by Mac Donald et al (2004) and Ahearn et al (2005). These findings present interesting insights into the organizational form of contractors and contract price comparison. Farmers frequently contract with cooperatives, with about one to three quarters of all contracts being owned firms. The fact that prices received on contracts do not seem to be different based on the type of contractor provides indirect evidence of a cooperative benefit since the members do not have price penalties in contracting with cooperatives, but retain the upside potential of a patronage payment. From the foregoing, there is no doubt that cooperative membership enhances adoption behavior of cooperative farmers, hence the study.

Methodology

Survey research design was chosen in this research work. The study is made up of all rice farmers' cooperative societies in Enugu state that participated in FADAMA project. According

to State Department of Cooperative, there are 323 registered cooperative societies that participated in FADAMA programme out of which 48 were into rice farming. These 48 FADAMA rice farmers cooperative with membership strength of 964 constitute the population of the study. The sample size was determined through a multi-stage sampling technique. The first Stage involves a purposive selection of two LGAs that are predominantly rural and agrarian from each of the three agricultural zones in Enugu State. Second stage involved random selection of cooperatives in the selected local government area that participated in FADAMA programme.. The third stage involved selecting the cooperative societies that were into rice farming. Therefore, a total of 331 members were selected from 24 rice farmers cooperatives who participated in FADAMA programme as sample size. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in achieving the objective of the study. Regression, frequency distribution, percentages and mean score rating were used.

Model Specification

The hypothesis which sought to measure the effect of cooperative on adoption of improved agricultural technologies was tested using regression equation. The three (3) functional forms used for the analysis which include linear, semi-log and double log.

1. The linear form is given by

$$Y = f(x_1 x_2 x_3 x_4 x_5 + \dots \dots \dots \text{ie) implicit}$$

$$Y = b_0 + b_{1x_1} + b_{2x_2} + b_{3x_3} + b_{4x_4} + b_{5x_5} + \dots \dots \dots \text{ei) explicit}$$

2. The semi-log form

$$Y = b_0 + b_1 \log x_1 + b_2 \log x_2 + b_3 \log x_3 + b_4 \log x_4 \dots \dots \dots \text{ei)$$

3. The double log form

$$\text{Log } y = b_0 + b_1 \log x_1 + b_2 \log x_2 + b_3 \log x_3 + b_4 \log x_4 + b_5 \log x_5 \dots \dots \dots + e_i$$

Y level of adoption of technologies measured by number of technologies adopted by the farmers' cooperative societies.

A = constant

$B_1 = B_n$ = Regression coefficient to be estimated

X_1 – Sex (no)

X_2 – Age (years)

X_3 – Level of education (no of years spent in school)

X_4 – Farm size (ha)

X_5 – Annual Farm Income (₦)

X_6 – Extension contact (no of visit)

X_7 – duration in cooperative

X_8 - Volume of output

The model of best fit was the linear model so it was chosen based on statistical and econometric criteria such as the number of significant variables the signs of the number of the regression coefficient as they conform to a priori expectations and the magnitude of the coefficient of multiple determinations R^2 .

Table 1 Extent of adoption of improved agricultural technologies among cooperative rice farmers in Enugu State

S/N		Mean	Standard deviation	Decision
1	Spacing	2.90	0.895	Low
2	Varieties	3.53	0.675	High
3	Line planting	4.45	0.785	High
4	Fertilizer application	3.62	0.870	High
5	Lime application	2.23	1.065	Low

Field survey: 2017.

According to Table 1, the extent of adoption of use of improved varieties, line planting and fertilizer application by cooperative rice farmers in Enugu State was high. The table showed

that adoption of spacing and lime application was low in the area. The use of line planting and fertilizer application rank high among the improved agricultural technologies adopted by cooperative rice farmers in the area of study.

Table 2 Contributions of cooperative to adoption of improved agricultural technologies

	Frequency	Mean	SD	Remark
Awareness creation	320	4.2	2.908	Accept
Sharing of ideas	320	2.7	2.871	Reject
Mitigating hindrances /objections	320	3.9	1.093	Accept
Provision of guarantee	320	3.4	3.983	Accept
Bargaining for cheaper cost of adoption	320	4.1	2.351	Accept
Convincing laggards and late adopters	320	4.7	3.981	Accept
Peer pressure towards adoption	320	4.1	0.378	Accept
Cheaper platform to achieve mechanization/modernization	320	4.4	4.936	Accept
Access to reliable experts	320	2.7	2.187	Reject
Provision of accessible experiment/practical	320	1.8	3.916	Reject
Platform for accessing adoption support services	320	4.2	2.871	Accept
Access to government /donor aids and assistance	320	3.9	3.157	Accept

Field survey: 2017.

Table 2 revealed that agricultural cooperatives contribute to awareness creation, mitigating objections to adoption, providing guarantee and cheaper platform to access adoption service. Respondents also agreed that cooperatives provides access to government aids and assistance as well as convince laggard on the need to adopt new technologies. However, majority of the respondents insisted that agricultural cooperatives do not contribute in sharing adoption ideas nor provide access to reliable experts and accessible experiment.

Test of hypothesis

H_{01} : Cooperatives do not have significant effect on adoption level of agricultural technologies among FADAMA rice farmers in Enugu State.

Table 3 Regression Estimates (Effects of cooperatives on adoption of improved technologies)

Model	Coefficient Estimates	t-Value	Significance
(CONSTANT)	1.187	5.023	0.030
Sex	0.184	1.904	0.273
Marital	0.206	1.860	0.428
Education	2.016	4.121	0.039
Housize	3.099	3.763	0.178
Farmexp	1.713	4.871	0.016
Coopdura	2.205	6.194	0.026
Age	0.421	1.437	0.076
Annual income	3.190	1.87	0.023
Output volume	0.425	1.246	0.149
Contact frequency	2.670	3.761	0.029
R^2	0.782		
Adj R^2	0.767		
F	22.774 (Sig. @ 0.05)		

Dependent Variable: Annual Rural farm income

The estimates of R^2 and Adj. R^2 suggest that all the variables in the model collectively accounted for more than 78% of the variations farm income. The F ratio value of 22.774 was significant at 5% level. All the variables had expected positive signs suggesting direct relationships with adoption level of agricultural technologies. However, only education, annual income, contact frequency, farm experience, age and cooperative duration were significant. Sex of the farmer, marital status and household size were not significant. This, therefore suggest that some socio-economic characteristics of farmers especially the number of years spent in cooperatives have influence on rural farm income. So we conclude that cooperatives have effect on adoption level of agricultural technologies.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Findings indicate that cooperative membership had significant effect on adoption of improved agricultural technologies. Cooperative members have high propensity to adopt new agricultural technologies than non members. Cooperatives contribute to adoption, sharing of information, motivating people towards adoption and providing platform for aid and assistance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Cooperative societies should maximize every opportunity they have to get their members trained and acquire skills. There is growing need for enhancing members' technical skills and regular training in cooperative knowledge to help them gain a better understanding of the cooperative's function. Farming is an occupation that needs improved skills and training is important to reduce individualism and increase large scale farming. This will improve the quality of member's participation and steer the cooperatives toward success.

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